

PROMOTING SUSTAINABLE ADAPTATION THROUGH CLIMATE CHANGE EDUCATION: FOUNDATION FOR STRATEGIC PLAN

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ABSTRACT

Climate change, one of the most significant challenges of the 21st century, continues to accelerate, affecting both ecological and socio-economic systems worldwide. This study explores the level of awareness and attitudes towards climate change adaptation among stakeholders—students, teachers, and parents—from two geographically and culturally distinct regions: Pampanga, Philippines, and Chevak, Alaska, USA. The study utilized a concurrent triangulation mixed-methods approach, combining quantitative surveys and qualitative interviews, to assess the respondents' knowledge and perceptions of climate change impacts and their readiness to adopt sustainable adaptation practices. Findings of the study revealed that while respondents in both regions recognized the threat posed by climate change, significant differences were noted in the depth of understanding and proactive engagement in adaptation strategies. Stakeholders in Chevak demonstrated lower awareness levels compared to their counterparts in Pampanga, largely due to varying levels of climate education and direct experience with environmental disasters. The study underscores the need for context-specific climate change education programs, particularly in vulnerable regions like Alaska, where climate impacts are felt more acutely yet awareness remains limited. Based on the results, the research proposes targeted educational interventions to enhance the capacity of these communities to adapt to the changing climate. By fostering climate resilience through education, communities can better prepare for future challenges, mitigate potential risks, and actively participate in global sustainability efforts. This research study contributes to the growing body of literature on climate change education by highlighting the importance of localized, culturally responsive approaches to raising awareness and promoting sustainable adaptation practices.

INTRODUCTION

The world has faced one of its most urgent challenges, climate change. Numerous studies have demonstrated that this global phenomenon has resulted in unprecedented temperature increases, intensifying existing vulnerabilities and introducing new environmental risks (Hosen et al., 2020). Due to climate change, existing vulnerability is worsened by introducing new threats and rising resource volatility across time and location (Eriksen et al., 2015). The widespread impacts of climate change have permeated ecological and social systems globally, manifesting through rising sea levels, altered weather patterns, and increased frequency and severity of extreme events such as floods and droughts (Nurse et al., 2014; Dietz et al., 2020). These effects have far-reaching consequences, particularly in regions highly susceptible to environmental disruptions.

Education has been recognized as a critical tool in combating climate change, particularly by fostering knowledge, critical thinking, and problem-solving skills among younger generations who will face the most significant impacts of this crisis (Stevenson et al., 2017). In various countries, including the Philippines, climate change has become integral to sustainability education, providing concrete examples of how unsustainable practices contribute to environmental degradation (McCright et al., 2013 as cited in Coleman et al., 2017).

The Philippines has been highly vulnerable to environmental hazards such as floods, often exacerbated by heavy rainfall and inefficient waste management (Cruz & Tantengco, 2017). In response to these challenges, schools have played a pivotal role in climate change education, equipping students, parents, and educators with knowledge and strategies for climate adaptation (Stevenson et al., 2017). This study aimed to assess the awareness and attitudes of key stakeholders in two distinct public schools—one located in Pampanga, Philippines, and the other in Chevak, Alaska—toward climate change. By comparing the awareness levels of these geographically diverse groups, the study sought to identify knowledge gaps and propose targeted interventions to enhance sustainability education and adaptation practices.

Research Questions

1. How may the profile of respondents be described in terms of:
 - 1.1 Age;
 - 1.2 Gender;
 - 1.3 Civil status; and
 - 1.4 Educational attainment?
2. What is the level of awareness on climate change adaptation among students, parents, and teachers in Dr. Clemente N. Dayrit Memorial High School and Chevak School?

3. What is the attitude of students, parents, and teachers towards community-based adaptation in Dr. Clemente N. Dayrit Memorial High School and Chevak School?
4. Is there a significant difference in the level of awareness and attitudes of students, parents, and teachers at Chevak School?
5. How may the observation on the current climate today be described by the participants?
6. How do participants adapt to climate change?
7. What training or seminar can be proposed to enhance the community-based climate change adaptation in the Chevak Native Village?
8. How may the Climate Change Education (CCE) on sustainable adaptation training and seminar be evaluated?

METHODOLOGY

The study employed a concurrent triangulation mixed-methods research design, integrating both quantitative and qualitative approaches to ensure a comprehensive analysis of the research problem. This design was selected to leverage the strengths of each method while compensating for their individual limitations, thereby providing a robust and nuanced understanding of climate change adaptation awareness and attitudes among the participants. Data collection was conducted through surveys and interviews. The quantitative component involved the administration of two validated instruments, the Climate Change Adaptation Awareness Questionnaire (CCAAQ) and the Attitude to Climate Change Adaptation Questionnaire (ACCQ), both adapted from the work of Eugenia and Onyegegbu (2021). These instruments demonstrated high internal consistency, with Cronbach's alpha values of 0.96 and 0.97, respectively.

The sample size of 111 respondents from Chevak School was determined using systematic random sampling, ensuring a representative selection of students, parents, and teachers. The qualitative component utilized purposive sampling to identify key informants, including Parent-Teacher Association (PTA) officers and student regents, who provided in-depth insights through semi-structured interviews. Quantitative data were subjected to descriptive statistical analysis, including frequency distributions, percentages, and means. A t-test was employed to determine significant differences in awareness and attitudes among the respondent groups. Qualitative data were analyzed using thematic analysis, following a six-phase process that involved coding and identifying patterns to extract meaningful themes related to climate change adaptation practices and perceptions. The integration of these methods allowed for a triangulation of findings, thereby enhancing the validity and reliability of the study's conclusions.

RESULTS

Table 1
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Respondents' Demographic Profile from Clemente N. Dayrit Memorial High School

Profile of Respondents	Frequency	Percent
Age		
<= 23	352	85
24 – 34	32	7.7
35 – 45	30	7.2
Gender		
Female	220	53.1
Male	188	45.4
Prefer not to say	6	1.4
Civil Status		
Married	7	1.7
Single	407	98.3
Educational Attainment		
Grade 7	88	21.3
Grade 8	85	20.5
Grade 9	95	22.9
Grade 10	84	20.3
College	19	4.6
Masters	26	6.3
Doctorate	17	4.1
Type of Respondent		
Parent	6	1.4
Student	350	84.5
Teacher	58	14
Total	414	100

Table 2
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Respondents' Demographic Profile from Chevok School

Age	Frequency	Percent
<= 23.00	91	82
24.00 - 34.00	9	8.1
35.00 - 45.00	11	9.9
Gender	Frequency	Percent
Female	54	48.6
Male	57	51.4
Civil Status	Frequency	Percent
Married	14	12.6
Single	97	87.4
Educational Attainment	Frequency	Percent
Grade 7	23	20.7
Grade 8	21	18.9
Grade 9	22	19.8
Grade 10	25	22.5
College	12	10.8
Masters	8	7.2
Type of Respondents	Frequency	Percent
Parent	10	9
Student	91	82
Teacher	10	9
Total	111	100

Table 3
Descriptive Measures of the Level of Awareness on Climate Change in Dr. Clemente N. Dayrit Memorial High School

Indicator	Mean	Interpretation
1. Establishing weather monitoring equipment in school compounds to forecast events in the atmosphere	3.23	Neutral
2. Knowledge of routine measures of water levels	3.26	Neutral
3. Strengthening early warning sign	3.44	Neutral
4. Creating awareness among the citizenry	3.42	Neutral
5. Switching to early maturing varieties of crops	3.23	Neutral
6. Tree planting and reforestation	3.68	Agree
7. Building of sea banks	3.05	Neutral
8. Encouraging recovery of by- products and scraps for reuse	3.35	Neutral
9. Encouraging recycle of waste materials	3.64	Agree

10. Planting trees that thrive on erosion lands e.g., Bamboo tree	3.52	Agree
11. Decrease the use of old cars	3.03	Neutral
12. Conservation of the remaining forest	3.36	Neutral
13. Restraining the use of air conditioner	3.16	Neutral
14. Proper disposal of waste in the environment	3.55	Agree
15. Increased use of wind energy	3.32	Neutral
16. Awareness campaign on climate change	3.54	Agree
17. Mapping of risk and disaster areas	3.39	Neutral
18. Formation of climate change clubs in schools and localities	3.38	Neutral
19. Mounting awareness campaigns through the radio and television on climate change adaptation	3.39	Neutral
20. Sticking to master plans of towns and cities	3.26	Neutral
21. Stop dumping of refuse in the drains	3.40	Neutral
22. Ensure that drains are cleared regularly	3.50	Agree
23. Making policy and programs that provide opportunities for the displaced communities to earn livelihood	3.44	Neutral
24. Construction of dikes to stop water flooding in low area of land	3.43	Neutral
25. Construction of embankments to keep water back against pollution of the wetland	3.34	Neutral
26. Construct fishponds in the flooded areas	3.02	Neutral
27. Explore other livelihoods other than agriculture	3.22	Neutral
28. Switch to other crops that can tolerate floods and heavy rainfall	3.27	Neutral
29. Provision of relief materials from good spirited individual and government	3.46	Agree
30. Free medicine from the government to flood victims	3.57	Agree
31. Rehabilitation of destroyed infrastructure by government	3.32	Neutral
32. Helping people in evacuation areas	3.57	Agree
33. Construction of surface dam	3.36	Neutral
34. Control the burning of bushes	3.42	Neutral
35. Proper timing of tree planting activities	3.52	Agree
36. Introduction of drought resistant plant species	3.43	Neutral
37. Planting early maturing varieties of crops and vegetables	3.46	Agree
38. Use of direct seeding method, which requires less water	3.43	Neutral
Weighted Mean	3.38	Neutral

Table 4*Descriptive Measures of the Level of Awareness on Climate Change in Chevak School*

Indicator	Mean	Interpretation
1. Establishing weather monitoring equipment in school compounds to forecast events in the atmosphere	2.21	Disagree
2. Knowledge of routine measures of water levels	1.62	Disagree
3. Strengthening early warning sign	1.82	Disagree
4. Creating awareness among the citizenry	1.67	Disagree
5. Switching to early maturing varieties of crops	1.88	Disagree
6. Tree planting and reforestation	1.91	Disagree
7. Building of sea banks	1.91	Disagree
8. Encouraging recovery of by- products and scraps for reuse	1.93	Disagree
9. Encouraging recycle of waste materials	1.68	Disagree
10. Planting trees that thrive on erosion lands e.g., Bamboo tree	1.76	Disagree
11. Decrease the use of old cars	1.82	Disagree
12. Conservation of the remaining forest	1.91	Disagree
13. Restraining the use of air conditioner	1.79	Disagree
14. Proper disposal of waste in the environment	1.68	Disagree
15. Increased use of wind energy	1.86	Disagree
16. Awareness campaign on climate change	1.95	Disagree
17. Mapping of risk and disaster areas	1.85	Disagree
18. Formation of climate change clubs in schools and localities	1.75	Disagree
19. Mounting awareness campaigns through the radio and television on climate change adaptation	1.90	Disagree
20. Sticking to master plans of towns and cities	1.92	Disagree
21. Stop dumping of refuse in the drains	2.04	Disagree
22. Ensure that drains are cleared regularly	1.73	Disagree
23. Making policy and programs that provide opportunities for the displaced communities to earn livelihood	1.89	Disagree
24. Construction of dikes to stop water flooding in low area of land	1.76	Disagree
25. Construction of embankments to keep water back against pollution of the wetland	1.67	Disagree
26. Construct fishponds in the flooded areas	1.72	Disagree
27. Explore other livelihoods other than agriculture	2.03	Disagree
28. Switch to other crops that can tolerate floods and heavy rainfall	1.82	Disagree
29. Provision of relief materials from good spirited individual and government	1.68	Disagree
30. Free medicine from government to flood victims	1.73	Disagree
31. Rehabilitation of destroyed infrastructure by government	1.75	Disagree
32. Helping people in evacuation areas	1.62	Disagree
33. Construction of surface dam	2.00	Disagree
34. Control burning of bushes	1.68	Disagree
35. Proper timing of tree planting activities	1.77	Disagree
36. Introduction of drought resistant plant species	1.77	Disagree
37. Planting early maturing varieties of crops and vegetables	1.76	Disagree
38. Use of direct seeding method, which requires less water	1.82	Disagree
Weighted Mean	1.82	Disagree

Table 5
Descriptive Measures of the Attitudes Towards Climate Change in Dr. Clemente N. Dayrit Memorial High School

Indicator	Mean	Interpretation
1. I do not think that proper environment management could stop the impact of climate change	2.34	Disagree
2. I am worried at the rate of flooding because it increases the effect of climate change.	3.27	Neutral
3. I always ask questions on Climate change adaptation strategies.	3.09	Neutral
4. I predicate in planting of trees on open fields in order to check the incidence of erosion.	3.25	Neutral
5. I believe that harnessing climate change impact will bring about safe environment.	3.25	Neutral
6. I am seriously concerned with the problem climate change may bring.	3.41	Neutral
7. I am working hard to educate my friends about Climate change adaptation.	3.29	Neutral
8. I have joined Climate change adaptation awareness club in my school to help.	3.11	Neutral
9. There is nothing I can do about Climate change adaptation that will make a meaningful difference.	2.57	Neutral
10. I am spreading the news of Climate change.	3.36	Neutral
11. I have heard of climate change adaptation before.	3.24	Neutral
12. I do not like to listen to news related to Climate change adaptation.	2.28	Disagree
13. I believe that the problem of Climate change adaptation will be easy to handle.	2.57	Neutral
14. I am spreading news of Climate change adaptation within my area.	3.15	Neutral
15. I don't mind engaging in any activity to ensure proper climate change adaptation.	2.84	Neutral
16. Climate change adaptation will benefit only those who caused it.	2.51	Neutral
17. I think non adherence to Climate change adaptation strategies will make a lot of people to lose their job.	2.82	Neutral
18. I always plant trees to help reduce the rate of Climate change.	3.24	Neutral
19. I will be happy if the issue of Climate change is taken more seriously in my school.	3.37	Neutral
20. I do not think I can do any meaningful thing to make difference about climate change.	2.50	Neutral
21. I am preparing myself to manage the effects of Climate change.	3.30	Neutral
22. I read any available information on Climate change.	3.31	Neutral
23. I read any available information on Climate change adaptation.	3.26	Neutral
24. I encourage my friends to stop bush burning to prevent Climate change.	3.34	Neutral
25. I will like the government to make an environmental laws against anybody who will cause climate change.	3.29	Neutral
26. I do not think that the climate is changing.	2.49	Neutral

27. I do not feel threatened about the problems caused by Climate change e.g flooding, erosion.	2.37	Disagree
28. I try to manage my classroom to avoid climate change effect.	3.24	Neutral
Weighted Mean	3.24	Neutral

Table 6
Descriptive Measures of the Attitudes Towards Climate Change in Chevak School

Indicator	Mean	Interpretation
1. I do not think that proper environment management could stop the impact of climate change	2.34	Disagree
2. I am worried at the rate of flooding because it increases the effect of climate change.	3.27	Neutral
3. I always ask questions on Climate change adaptation strategies.	3.09	Neutral
4. I predicate in planting of trees on open fields in order to check the incidence of erosion.	3.25	Neutral
5. I believe that harnessing climate change impact will bring about safe environment.	3.25	Neutral
6. I am seriously concerned with the problem climate change may bring.	3.41	Neutral
7. I am working hard to educate my friends about Climate change adaptation.	3.29	Neutral
8. I have joined Climate change adaptation awareness club in my school to help.	3.11	Neutral
9. There is nothing I can do about Climate change adaptation that will make a meaningful difference.	2.57	Neutral
10. I am spreading the news of Climate change.	3.36	Neutral
11. I have heard of climate change adaptation before.	3.24	Neutral
12. I do not like to listen to news related to Climate change adaptation.	2.28	Disagree
13. I believe that the problem of Climate change adaptation will be easy to handle.	2.57	Neutral
14. I am spreading news of Climate change adaptation within my area.	3.15	Neutral
15. I don't mind engaging in any activity to ensure proper climate change adaptation.	2.84	Neutral
16. Climate change adaptation will benefit only those who caused it.	2.51	Neutral
17. I think non adherence to Climate change adaptation strategies will make a lot of people to lose their job.	2.82	Neutral
18. I always plant trees to help reduce the rate of Climate change.	3.24	Neutral
19. I will be happy if the issue of Climate change is taken more seriously in my school.	3.37	Neutral
20. I do not think I can do any meaningful thing to make difference about climate change.	2.50	Neutral
21. I am preparing myself to manage the effects of Climate change.	3.30	Neutral
22. I read any available information on Climate change.	3.31	Neutral
23. I read any available information on Climate change adaptation.	3.26	Neutral

24. I encourage my friends to stop bush burning to prevent Climate change.	3.34	Neutral
25. I will like the government to make an environmental laws against anybody who will cause climate change.	3.29	Neutral
26. I do not think that the climate is changing.	2.49	Neutral
27. I do not feel threatened about the problems caused by Climate change e.g flooding, erosion.	2.37	Disagree
28. I try to manage my classroom to avoid climate change effect.	3.24	Neutral
Weighted Mean	3.24	Neutral

Table 7
Significant Difference in the Level of Awareness and Attitude of the Parents by School toward Climate Change

Group Statistics^a

	School	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Climate Change Awareness	Dr. Clemente N. Dayrit	6	74.0000	6.41872	2.62043
	Memorial High School				
	Chevak School	10	69.9000	5.06513	1.60174
Attitude towards Climate Change	Dr. Clemente N. Dayrit	6	47.6667	3.01109	1.22927
	Memorial High School				
	Chevak School	10	48.2000	3.25918	1.03064

a. Type of Respondent = Parent

Table 8
T-test Results on Parents' Level of Awareness and Attitudes toward Climate Change

Independent Samples Test^a

		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means						
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
									Lower	Upper
Climate Change Awareness	Equal variances assumed	2.025	.177	1.421	14	.177	4.10000	2.88477	-2.08722	10.28722
	Equal variances not assumed			1.335	8.755	.216	4.10000	3.07119	-2.87724	11.07724

Attitude towards Climate Change	Equal variances assumed	.218	.648	-.326	14	.750	-.53333	1.63843	-	4.04741	2.98074
	Equal variances not assumed			-.332	11.377	.746	-.53333	1.60416	-	4.04985	2.98318

a. Type of Respondent = Parent

Table 9

Significant Difference in the Level of Awareness and Attitude of the Students by School toward Climate Change

Group Statistics^a

	School	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Climate Change Awareness	Dr. Clemente N. Dayrit Memorial High School	350	137.5886	42.03296	2.24676
	Chevak School	91	68.7912	5.77642	.60553
Attitude towards Climate Change	Dr. Clemente N. Dayrit Memorial High School	350	89.6629	22.55107	1.20541
	Chevak School	91	49.4725	5.71614	.59921

a. Type of Respondent = Student

Table 10

T-test Results on Students' Level of Awareness and Attitudes toward Climate Change

Independent Samples Test^a

		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means						
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
									Lower	Upper
Climate Change Awareness	Equal variances assumed	178.831	.000	15.563	439	.000	68.79736	4.42069	60.10902	77.48571
	Equal variances not assumed			29.566	393.492	.000	68.79736	2.32693	64.22260	73.37213
Attitude towards Climate Change	Equal variances assumed	69.776	.000	16.848	439	.000	40.19033	2.38551	35.50190	44.87876
	Equal variances not assumed			29.856	438.873	.000	40.19033	1.34613	37.54467	42.83599

a. Type of Respondent = Student

Table 11
Significant Difference in the Level of Awareness and Attitude of the Teachers by School toward Climate Change

Group Statistics ^a					
	School	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Climate Change Awareness	Dr. Clemente N. Dayrit Memorial High School	58	78.2414	27.20508	3.57220
	Chevak School	10	70.4000	6.11374	1.93333
Attitude towards Climate Change	Dr. Clemente N. Dayrit Memorial High School	58	54.0517	13.14617	1.72618
	Chevak School	10	48.2000	3.25918	1.03064

a. Type of Respondent = Teacher

Table 12
T-test Results on Teachers' Level of Awareness and Attitudes toward Climate Change

		Independent Samples Test ^a								
		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means						
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
									Lower	Upper
Climate Change Awareness	Equal variances assumed	3.028	.086	.902	66	.370	7.84138	8.69122	-9.51119	25.19395
	Equal variances not assumed			1.931	61.736	.058	7.84138	4.06182	-.27878	15.96154
Attitude towards Climate Change	Equal variances assumed	3.387	.070	1.392	66	.169	5.85172	4.20342	-2.54067	14.24412
	Equal variances not assumed			2.911	58.112	.005	5.85172	2.01045	1.82754	9.87591

a. Type of Respondent = Teacher

Table 13
Participants' observation about the current climate today

Probing Questions	Participants	Codes	Emergent Theme
What have you noticed about our climate today?	It is warmer & early spring kind of weather. The Summer times are much warmer than the other years. Also, many years ago we used to have strong winter storms for weeks at a time. We have small storms & they don't last long.	The Weather is Getting Warmer	
	The climate in Chevak is becoming unusual during winter season, it is not right away snow it is very warm.	The Weather is Getting Warmer	
	The environment is becoming hotter and hotter. We are having problem with our subsistence activities.	The Weather is Getting Warmer	
	The climate in Chevak is becoming unusual during winter season, it is not right away snow it is very warm.	The Weather is Getting Warmer	
	The climate in Chevak is becoming unusual during winter season, it is not right away snow it is very warm.	The Weather is Getting Warmer	Warm Weather
	Sometimes its too hot and too cold and always rainy	The Weather is Changing	
	Our climate has been constantly changing	The Weather is Changing	
	Pabago-bago Minsan malamig Minsan mainit o umuuulan (The weather is changing, sometimes its hot, sometimes its rainy)	The Weather is Changing	

Ang pag babago ng klima ay ang malawakang pagbago sa panahon sa mundo.	The Weather is Changing	Changing Weather
This refers in changing tempersture and weather because of different human activities that abuse to our environment.	The Weather is Changing	
Climate Change is a study on the changes of weather pattern in a longer period of time in a global scale.	The Weather is Changing	
It is long-term changes in temperature and weather patterns. This climate phenomena is caused by too much emission of greenhouse gases.	The Weather is Changing	
Changes in weather patterns	The Weather is Changing	
it is a change in temperature and weather pattern that we have experience.	The Weather is Changing	
Pabago-bago Hindi tugma sa bawat buwan (The weather is changing, it doesn't match in the season)	The Weather is Changing	
Pa iba iba ng mga panahon, Minsan malamig minsan mainit (The seasons are different, sometimes cold sometimes hot).	The Weather is Changing	
it depends on the day if it's rainy or hot	The Weather is Changing	
It is different every year	The Weather is Changing	
Climate is changing, longer winter.	The Weather is Changing	

Our weather is changing.	The Weather is Changing
Our world is changing.	The Weather is Changing
Our climate change and increasing tremendously.	The Weather is Changing
Our climate here in our village is changing every year.	The Weather is Changing
Global climate change is changing/dynamic and the change is evident across a wide range of observations. The global warming of the 50 years is primarily due to human activities. The direct consequences of man-made climate change include: rising of the minimum temperatures, rising of sea levels, higher ocean temperature, heavy rain/ hail and humidity is increasing.	The Weather is Changing
Long summers, much less snow and losing a lot of land all from climate change.	The Weather is Changing
Not much snow last year. I think thats all	The Weather is Changing
I observed the weather got colder.	The weather is getting colder
I observed wet to cold winters	The weather is getting colder

I noticed that it's getting colder this January	The weather is getting colder	Cold Weather
I've noticed how it is changing. Unlike how before, when you say December, people would automatically think that we'll have a cold climate for the whole month. The past few years, we had quite a warm climate during those times.	The weather is getting colder	
I have observed that we still have a cold climate even though it's almost summer.	The weather is getting colder	

Table 14
Participants' Adaptation Strategies in Climate Change

Probing Questions	Participants	Codes	Emergent Theme
How do you adapt to climate change?	The houses that are built now are much better than the older models because of the weather change; many of the families use wood stoves because the price of stove oil is high.	Promoting Sustainable and Efficient Living	
	Upgrading my life example from using a fan to air conditioning.	Promoting Sustainable and Efficient Living	
	By conserving the use of electricity and less use of machines or vehicles that would produce pollution, about using gas or oil that would produce pollution.	Promoting Sustainable and Efficient Living	

<p>We would use less heat, add more cool air, and learn to have whatever we got.</p>	<p>Promoting Sustainable and Efficient Living</p>	
<p>There are many ways to adapt to what is happening and what will happen. I adapt to the changing climate by planting trees or preserving trees around my home. I also do reuse, reduce and recycle.</p>	<p>Promoting Sustainable and Efficient Living</p>	
<p>There are alot of ways to adapt to the changing of climate like reducing waste, planting crops and even create a group that gives out information about climate change.</p>	<p>Promoting Sustainable and Efficient Living</p>	<p>Sustainable and Efficient Living</p>
<p>Halimbawa, ang isa sa mga indibidwal na pagkilos na magagawa mo upang labanan ang pagbabago ng klima ay ang maayos na pag-recycle ng basurang nabuo sa iyong tahanan.</p>	<p>Promoting Sustainable and Efficient Living</p>	
<p>Halimbawa, ang isa sa mga indibidwal na pagkilos na magagawa mo upang labanan ang pagbabago ng klima ay ang maayos na pag-recycle ng basurang nabuo sa iyong tahanan.</p>	<p>Promoting Sustainable and Efficient Living</p>	
<p>Nakakatulong ito sa mga ibang puno at halaman at sa ibang tao</p>	<p>Promoting Sustainable and Efficient Living</p>	

In educating Junior High School Students, we integrate tree planting into our lessons. We craft programs, projects, and activities concerning climate change mitigation.	Promoting Sustainable and Efficient Living	
Reduced the number of CO2 emissions and plant more trees	Promoting Sustainable and Efficient Living	
Adaptation in order to adjust and survive in the environment.	Knowledge/Awareness about Climate Change Adaptation	Climate Change Education
I adapt by everyday experience through it	Knowledge/Awareness about Climate Change Adaptation	
I adapt by becoming informed of the situation and doing the thing that are necessary to solution the problem that causes climate change	Knowledge /Awareness about Climate Change Adaptation	
I do not know the specific ways to adapt.	Knowledge /Awareness Climate Change Adaptation	
I do not know how to adapt in the changing climate. For I realized that is natural.	Knowledge /Awareness about Climate Change Adaptation	
I don't know anything about adapting.	Knowledge /Awareness about Climate Change Adaptation	

By wearing appropriate clothing during warm or cold climates	Knowledge /Awareness about Climate Change Adaptation	
Pag sunod upang mabawasan ang mga pangyayari sa klima sumunod sa binigay na tips.	Knowledge /Awareness about Climate Change Adaptation	
Sa pag sunod sa ating mga ali tuntunin sa labas, at paglalagay ng mga babala upang maiwasan natin ang patuloy na pag papalit ng klima at temperatura sa ating panahon	Knowledge /Awareness about Climate Change Adaptation	
Kailangan to malaman para malaman rin nang iba, para ipag sabi nila sa iba para hindi na sila gumawa nang nakakasama sa klima.	Knowledge /Awareness about Climate Change Adaptation	
I will have to get used to the different seasons and get used to the animals that were here and now gone but in time we can adapt to it the animals do not know how to adapt as we do they adapt slowly.	Acceptance and Adjustment to Changing Climate Conditions	Climate Change Adaptation
We all want adapt to the climate change.	Acceptance and Adjustment to Changing Climate Conditions	

Adapting to climate change is something that can be hard to adapt . Adapting can be hard especially in our environment.	Acceptance and Adjustment to Changing Climate Conditions
I will miss the climate but climate has to change.	Acceptance and Adjustment to Changing Climate Conditions
You adapt by learning the climate change. Then just roll with it.	Acceptance and Adjustment to Changing Climate Conditions
You adapt by being aware about the climate change.	Acceptance and Adjustment to Changing Climate Conditions
You adapt by learning the climate change. Then just roll with it.	Acceptance and Adjustment to Changing Climate Conditions

Table 15
Descriptive Measures of the Evaluation of the Training/Seminar on Climate Change Adaptation

Indicator	Mean	Interpretation
1. The objectives of the training/seminar were clearly defined.	4.52	Outstanding
2. Participation and interaction were encouraged.	4.50	Very Satisfactory
3. The topics covered were relevant to me.	4.25	Very Satisfactory
4. The content was organized and easy to follow.	4.50	Very Satisfactory

5. The materials distributed were helpful.	4.52	Outstanding
6. This training experience will be useful in my work/schooling.	4.62	Outstanding
7. The trainer was knowledgeable about the training climate change adaptation topics.	4.55	Outstanding
8. The trainer was well prepared.	4.57	Outstanding
9. The training objectives were met.	4.75	Outstanding
10. The time allotted for the training was sufficient.	4.27	Very Satisfactory
11. The meeting room and facilities were adequate and comfortable.	4.47	Very Satisfactory
Weighted Mean	4.48	Very Satisfactory

Figure 1
Proposed Action Plan

Action Plan (Training/Seminar on Climate Change Adaptation)

Promoting Sustainable Adaptation Through Climate Change Education

Introduction

Promoting sustainable adaptation through climate change education is crucial in addressing the challenges of climate change. As the impacts of climate change continue escalating, it is essential to equip individuals and communities with the knowledge, skills, and attitudes necessary to adapt sustainably and sustainably. Climate change education is vital in understanding, raising awareness, and empowering individuals to make informed decisions and take effective action. By integrating sustainability principles into climate change education, people can promote adaptive strategies that reduce vulnerability and environmental, social, and economic well-being.

DISCUSSION

The demographic profile of respondents, as shown in Table 1, reveals that the study is predominantly focused on younger individuals, with 85% aged 23 years or younger, most of whom are students (84.5%). The gender distribution is relatively balanced, with 53.1% female and 45.4% male, while a small percentage (1.4%) preferred not to disclose their gender. Most respondents have completed secondary education, with only a small proportion having attained college or higher degrees. The overwhelming majority are single (98.3%), consistent with the younger age group. The minimal

representation of parents (1.4%) and the stronger presence of teachers (14%) suggest that the perspectives captured primarily reflect student views on climate change, with limited input from older or more experienced individuals. This student-centered demographic in Table 1 will be key in analyzing the data on climate change awareness and attitudes, as younger respondents may have unique insights into climate education and its role in adaptation strategies.

The demographic profile of respondents from Chevak School, as shown in Table 2, indicates that many participants are young, with 82% aged 23 years or younger, which aligns with the 82% student representation in the sample. The gender distribution is almost balanced, with 51.4% male and 48.6% female respondents. In terms of civil status, most respondents (87.4%) are single, which is consistent with the younger age group. Regarding educational attainment, the majority are in Grades 7 to 10, with Grade 10 representing the highest portion at 22.5%. A smaller percentage (10.8%) have completed college, and 7.2% hold a master's degree. The respondent types are primarily students (82%), with parents and teachers both making up 9% of the total sample. This profile suggests a predominantly student-focused sample, with a fair gender distribution, and highlights the importance of considering the educational context when analyzing climate change awareness and adaptation in the Chevak community. Likewise, Ali & Erenstein (2017) found that wealthier farmers farm more land and have joint families; therefore, younger farmers and farmers with greater levels of education are more likely to utilize these adaptive strategies. Higher levels of education, male household heads, larger plots of land, larger families, and more access to extension services, credit, and wealth were all related to more adaptation practices being put into place.

The data from Table 3 shows the level of awareness on climate change at Dr. Clemente N. Dayrit Memorial High School, with a weighted mean of 3.38, indicating an overall neutral awareness level. Several indicators related to climate change adaptation strategies, such as establishing weather monitoring equipment (3.23), knowledge of routine water level measures (3.26), and the construction of dikes (3.43), are interpreted as neutral, reflecting a moderate level of awareness but not strong engagement. However, there are notable exceptions where respondents expressed agreement, such as tree planting and reforestation (3.68), recycling waste materials (3.64), proper disposal of waste (3.55), and free medicine for flood victims (3.57), suggesting a higher awareness of these specific environmental actions. The agreement on tree planting activities and climate change awareness campaigns (3.54) highlights areas where students and teachers are likely more actively involved or knowledgeable. According to Bustamante et al. (2019), climate change is a global phenomenon that affects biophysical systems and human well-being. Extensive tropical forest loss and degradation have increased awareness at the international level of the need to undertake large-scale ecological restoration, highlighting the need to identify cases in which restoration strategies can contribute to mitigation and adaptation. On the other hand, certain preventive measures, like building sea banks (3.05) and decreasing the use of old cars (3.03), scored lower, indicating a less robust understanding or prioritization of these strategies. Overall, the neutral weighted mean suggests that while there is awareness of climate change and

adaptation strategies, there is still room for improvement in fostering stronger engagement and knowledge across a wider range of environmental actions.

The data from Table 4 presents the level of awareness on climate change in Chevak School, with a weighted mean of 1.82, indicating a general disagreement regarding awareness of climate change adaptation measures. Across all 38 indicators, respondents consistently expressed low levels of awareness, with the majority of items scoring below 2.0. Indicators such as knowledge of routine water level measures (1.62), strengthening early warning systems (1.82), and creating awareness among the citizenry (1.67) highlight the lack of familiarity with critical climate change strategies. Even relatively simple actions, like tree planting and reforestation (1.91) and recycling (1.68), received low scores, pointing to a significant gap in environmental education and awareness. The highest-scoring item, stopping the dumping of refuse in drains (2.04), and the construction of surface dams (2.00) still fall within the disagree category, suggesting some awareness of environmental cleanliness but limited engagement with broader climate action. These results emphasize the urgent need for enhanced climate change education in Chevak School, as the low awareness levels indicate a lack of preparedness and understanding of essential adaptation strategies that could mitigate the impacts of climate change in this vulnerable region.

The results from Table 5 present the attitudes of respondents from Dr. Clemente N. Dayrit Memorial High School toward climate change, with a weighted mean of 3.24, indicating a generally neutral stance. Most items reflect a moderate level of concern and awareness, with respondents neither strongly agreeing nor disagreeing with most statements. For example, respondents showed neutral attitudes towards spreading awareness about climate change (3.36), engaging in tree planting (3.24), and preparing for the effects of climate change (3.30). However, some areas of concern, such as whether environmental management could mitigate climate change impacts (2.34), and whether climate change poses a personal threat (2.37), were met with disagreement, indicating skepticism or uncertainty about these specific aspects. Interestingly, although respondents are "seriously concerned with the problem climate change may bring" (3.41), they seem less confident in their individual ability to make meaningful changes (2.57). The general neutrality in the results suggests that while students may be aware of climate change, they may not feel fully empowered or informed enough to take decisive action or see immediate impacts of their efforts. Overall, the data point to a need for stronger education and encouragement to turn awareness into action.

The results from Table 6 reveal that the overall attitude towards climate change at Chevak School is predominantly neutral, with a weighted mean of 3.24. Most indicators reflect a moderate stance, where respondents neither strongly agree nor disagree with various statements about climate change adaptation. For instance, respondents expressed neutrality on issues such as the impact of climate change (3.41), engaging in climate change adaptation activities (3.29), and reading available information about climate change (3.31). There is some level of concern about climate change, as seen in statements like "I am worried at the rate of flooding because it increases the effect of climate change" (3.27), but respondents still express disagreement (2.34) with the idea

that proper environmental management could fully mitigate its impacts. Moreso, Arıkan and Günay (2021), discovered that climate change worry is boosted by people's perceptions of the dangers of climate change. Additionally, there is skepticism about personal involvement or making meaningful changes, with scores like 2.57 for "There is nothing I can do about climate change adaptation that will make a meaningful difference." This neutrality suggests that while respondents are somewhat aware of climate change issues, there may be a lack of strong conviction or empowerment to take proactive steps, indicating a need for greater education and motivation in climate action at Chevak School.

The data in Table 7 compares the level of climate change awareness and attitudes between parents from Dr. Clemente N. Dayrit Memorial High School and Chevak School. For climate change awareness, parents from Dr. Clemente N. Dayrit Memorial High School have a slightly higher mean score (74.00) compared to parents from Chevak School (69.90), although the difference is small. The standard deviation shows that there is slightly more variability in the responses from Dr. Clemente N. Dayrit Memorial High School (6.42) compared to Chevak School (5.07). In terms of attitudes toward climate change, the mean scores for both schools are quite similar, with Dr. Clemente N. Dayrit Memorial High School scoring 47.67 and Chevak School scoring 48.20. This suggests that, although there is a slight difference in awareness, the attitudes of parents toward climate change are generally consistent across both schools, indicating that parents in both settings may have similar views on climate change issues regardless of their slight differences in awareness.

The results in Table 8 present the t-test analysis for the significant difference in parents' level of awareness and attitudes toward climate change between Dr. Clemente N. Dayrit Memorial High School and Chevak School. For climate change awareness, the p-value (Sig. = .177) is greater than the alpha level of .05, indicating that there is no statistically significant difference in climate change awareness between parents from both schools, whether equal variances are assumed or not. Similarly, for attitudes toward climate change, the p-value (Sig. = .750) also exceeds the .05 threshold, showing no significant difference in attitudes between the two groups of parents. The mean difference for climate change awareness is 4.10, and for attitudes, it is -0.53, both of which are statistically insignificant. These results suggest that parents from both schools exhibit comparable levels of awareness and attitudes toward climate change, with no meaningful differences detected between the two groups.

The data in Table 9 presents a comparison of students' level of awareness and attitudes toward climate change between Dr. Clemente N. Dayrit Memorial High School and Chevak School. The results show a substantial difference in climate change awareness, with students from Dr. Clemente N. Dayrit Memorial High School having a much higher mean score (137.59) compared to students from Chevak School (68.79). This large disparity, coupled with the higher standard deviation (42.03) for Dr. Clemente N. Dayrit Memorial High School, suggests greater variability in awareness levels among its students compared to the more uniform awareness in Chevak School (standard deviation of 5.78). Similarly, attitudes toward climate change show a significant difference, with students from Dr. Clemente N. Dayrit Memorial High School having a higher mean

score (89.66) compared to those from Chevak School (49.47). The smaller standard deviations for Chevak School indicate that students' attitudes and awareness there are more consistent but notably lower than those in Dr. Clemente N. Dayrit Memorial High School. Overall, the results suggest that students from Dr. Clemente N. Dayrit Memorial High School are more aware and have a more positive attitude toward climate change compared to their counterparts in Chevak School.

The results in Table 10 present the t-test analysis for the significant difference in students' level of awareness and attitudes toward climate change between Dr. Clemente N. Dayrit Memorial High School and Chevak School. For climate change awareness, the p-value (Sig. = .000) is less than .05, indicating a statistically significant difference between the two schools. The mean difference of 68.80 shows that students from Dr. Clemente N. Dayrit Memorial High School are significantly more aware of climate change than those from Chevak School. Similarly, for attitudes toward climate change, the p-value (Sig. = .000) is also highly significant, with a mean difference of 40.19, demonstrating that students from Dr. Clemente N. Dayrit Memorial High School hold significantly more positive attitudes toward climate change compared to Chevak School students. The confidence intervals for both awareness and attitudes confirm this difference, as the ranges do not include zero. Overall, the results indicate that students from Dr. Clemente N. Dayrit Memorial High School are more aware and have more favorable attitudes towards climate change than students from Chevak School, with these differences being statistically significant.

The data in Table 11 compares the level of awareness and attitudes toward climate change between teachers from Dr. Clemente N. Dayrit Memorial High School and Chevak School. The results show that teachers from Dr. Clemente N. Dayrit Memorial High School have a higher mean score in climate change awareness (78.24) compared to teachers from Chevak School (70.40). The standard deviation is significantly larger for Dr. Clemente N. Dayrit Memorial High School (27.21), indicating more variability in the responses, whereas Chevak School teachers' awareness is more consistent with a lower standard deviation (6.11). Regarding attitudes toward climate change, teachers from Dr. Clemente N. Dayrit Memorial High School also have a higher mean score (54.05) compared to their Chevak counterparts (48.20), with a larger standard deviation for Dr. Clemente N. Dayrit Memorial High School (13.15), suggesting greater variation in attitudes. These results indicate that teachers at Dr. Clemente N. Dayrit Memorial High School generally show higher awareness and more positive attitudes toward climate change, but with more variability in their responses compared to the more consistent but lower levels of awareness and attitudes seen among Chevak School teachers.

The results in Table 12 present the t-test analysis for the significant difference in teachers' level of awareness and attitudes toward climate change between Dr. Clemente N. Dayrit Memorial High School and Chevak School. For climate change awareness, the p-value (Sig. = .370) is greater than .05, indicating that there is no statistically significant difference in awareness between the two groups of teachers. The mean difference of 7.84 suggests a slight difference in favor of Dr. Clemente N. Dayrit Memorial High School teachers, but it is not statistically significant. For attitudes toward climate change, the p-

value (Sig. = .169 for equal variances and .005 for unequal variances) shows mixed results. While equal variances assumed show no significant difference, the result for unequal variances suggests a statistically significant difference in attitudes, with Dr. Clemente N. Dayrit Memorial High School teachers having a more positive attitude compared to Chevak School teachers. The mean difference of 5.85 indicates that, while both groups of teachers have similar awareness, Dr. Clemente N. Dayrit Memorial High School teachers exhibit a more favorable attitude toward climate change adaptation.

The data in Table 13 presents participants' observations about the current climate, highlighting the emergent themes of “warm weather”, “changing weather”, and “cold weather”. A significant number of participants expressed that the climate is getting warmer, particularly noting that winters are becoming shorter and less intense, and summer temperatures are rising. This theme of warmer weather is prevalent, especially in Chevak, where participants observe unusual warmth during the winter season, which has affected subsistence activities. Additionally, many respondents commented on the “changing weather”, emphasizing the unpredictability of climate conditions, with some days being too hot or too cold, and seasons no longer matching typical patterns. There is a shared sentiment that these changes in weather patterns are influenced by climate change, as indicated by comments related to human activities and greenhouse gas emissions. Lastly, a few participants noted a trend towards “colder weather”, particularly during winter months, although this observation was less common than reports of warming and variability. Overall, the participants' experiences reflect a broad acknowledgment of climate change's impact, characterized by warming trends, unpredictable weather, and seasonal inconsistencies.

The data in Table 14 presents participants' adaptation strategies to climate change, with three key emergent themes: Promoting Sustainable and Efficient Living, Knowledge/Awareness about Climate Change Adaptation, and Acceptance and Adjustment to Changing Climate Conditions. A significant number of participants indicated that they adapt to climate change by adopting sustainable practices, such as using wood stoves to reduce reliance on expensive stove oil, conserving electricity, reducing waste, recycling, and planting trees. These responses highlight an emphasis on promoting sustainable and efficient living as a means of mitigating climate change effects. Additionally, some participants mentioned their efforts to educate others about climate change, particularly through initiatives like tree planting and climate-related lessons in schools. Another group of participants expressed a lack of specific knowledge about adaptation, showing that awareness about climate change adaptation still needs to be strengthened. Lastly, a few participants accepted climate change as inevitable and emphasized adapting by becoming informed and adjusting their behaviors and expectations to fit the changing environment, such as wearing appropriate clothing or adjusting to changes in wildlife. Overall, the responses reflect a combination of proactive efforts to adapt through sustainability and education, alongside a recognition of the need for further awareness and acceptance of the changing climate.

Furthermore, Figure 1 depicts the “Strategic Plan for a Training/Seminar on Climate Change Adaptation” that aims to promote sustainable adaptation through climate change

education. Its primary goal is to equip individuals, communities, and institutions with the necessary knowledge, skills, and attitudes to mitigate and adapt to the effects of climate change sustainably. The seminar objectives include raising awareness of sustainable practices, improving climate change literacy, integrating Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), fostering environmental consciousness, empowering educators, and engaging multiple stakeholders. The training consists of presentations, interactive activities, workshops, and hands-on practice sessions, such as vulnerability assessments and risk mapping, to encourage active participation and practical learning. Participants are provided with tools to assess climate-related risks, plan community engagement strategies, and collaborate on adaptation initiatives. The seminar also emphasizes feedback and evaluation to gauge its effectiveness and concludes with a recap of key takeaways, encouraging ongoing application of the knowledge gained.

The results in Table 15 show the participants' evaluation of the training/seminar on climate change adaptation, with an overall weighted mean of 4.48, indicating a very satisfactory rating. Key aspects such as the clarity of the objectives (4.52), the usefulness of the training for work or schooling (4.62), and the trainer's preparedness (4.57) were rated outstanding, reflecting high satisfaction with the training's effectiveness and relevance. Most participants also found the interaction and participation opportunities (4.50) and the organization of the content (4.50) to be very satisfactory. Although topics covered and the facilities received lower scores compared to other indicators, they still received a very satisfactory rating. Overall, the participants viewed the seminar as well-organized, informative, and beneficial, especially in enhancing their knowledge and preparedness for climate change adaptation.

Conclusions

The study's findings underscore a targeted focus on assessing the perspectives, knowledge, and attitudes of young students, particularly females, regarding climate change education and sustainable adaptation. It emphasizes the critical need for both Dr. Clemente N. Dayrit Memorial High School and Chevak School to intensify efforts in fostering climate change awareness, given the observed lack of strong engagement and alignment among stakeholders. While students at Dr. Clemente N. Dayrit Memorial High School exhibited significantly higher awareness and more favorable attitudes toward climate change compared to their counterparts at Chevak School, the differences in awareness and attitudes among teachers and parents were not statistically significant. Participants' observations confirmed shifts in weather patterns, reflecting both warming trends and variability, aligning with broader climate change phenomena. The recognition of the importance of adopting proactive adaptation strategies, including sustainable living practices, further highlights the necessity for continued education. Additionally, the training/seminar on climate change adaptation was positively evaluated, with participants affirming its value in deepening their understanding of adaptive measures.

Recommendations

The recommendations emphasize the importance of regularly assessing climate change education initiatives to improve their effectiveness in fostering sustainable adaptation. Dr. Clemente N. Dayrit Memorial High School and Chevak School should enhance climate change awareness, promote sustainability, and shift neutral attitudes by fostering better understanding and active involvement in climate change mitigation. Both schools should create supportive environments for teachers and engage communities in climate-related initiatives. Participants should deepen their understanding of climate change, adopt sustainable living practices, and be empowered to take individual and collective action. Finally, the training/seminar should continue to offer learning opportunities, networking, and collaboration to strengthen climate resilience and promote sustainable adaptation practices.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This research on promoting sustainable adaptation through climate change education, serving as the basis for an action plan, was conducted in full compliance with ethical standards. All research procedures adhered to established ethical guidelines, with informed consent obtained from all participants after clearly explaining the study's purpose, procedures, and their rights, including the option to withdraw without consequences. Participant confidentiality and privacy were strictly maintained, with all data anonymized to protect identities, especially given the sensitivity of discussing climate change impacts and adaptation strategies. The study followed institutional ethical protocols and received approval from the relevant ethics review board, ensuring transparency and accountability throughout. Emphasizing community engagement, the research captured the experiences and perspectives of participants to ensure that the action plan's proposed educational strategies were tailored to the community's specific needs and environmental challenges. There were no conflicts of interest or biases, and the research upheld principles of accuracy, honesty, and integrity, providing a sound and socially responsible foundation for advancing climate change education and promoting sustainable adaptation practices.

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